

Notes

Study of Hg(II) Chelate of Bidentate Schiff's Base

R. K. UPADHYAY

Department of Chemistry, N.R.E.C. College, Khurja, (U.P.),
&

R. C. SAXENA & R. R. SHARMA

Department of Chemistry, M. M. College, Modinagar, (U.P.)

Manuscript received 1 August 1972; revised 9 October 1972;
accepted 10 September 1973

HEXAHYDROANILINE and phenyl glyoxal have been condensed to synthesise the Schiff's base (SB) which is characterised by elemental analysis, I.R. and U.V. Its 2:4 dinitrophenylhydrazone, *p*-nitrophenylhydrazone, semicarbazone and oxime have also been prepared. SB forms dark blue 1:1 complex (chelate) with Hg(II) chloride. Conductometry and elemental analysis of the complex, have been used to find out metal-ligand ratio. Molar conductance and magnetic measurements are used to establish nature and stereochemistry.

Survey of literature reveals that transition or non-transition metal complexes of Schiff's bases have been studied for a long time. However, only few references¹⁻⁴ on Hg(II)-Schiff's base complexes are available, which might be due to closed shell electronic configuration of Hg(II) ion. It is therefore thought interesting to study less common Hg(II)-Schiff's base

complexes. Present paper describes the preparation and properties of the Hg(II) chelate of Schiff's base derived from hexahydroaniline and phenyl glyoxal⁵; characterisation of Schiff's base is also given in this paper.

Experimental

Preparation of SB: On mixing equimolecular quantities of hexahydroaniline and phenyl glyoxal in ethanol at room temperature, red coloured liquid was obtained; which was crystallised under vacuum. Crystalline mass (Schiff's base) is soluble in ethanol, methanol, benzene, acetone, carbon tetrachloride but insoluble in water and petroleum ether. Characteristics of SB are given in Table 1.

Derivative of SB: 2:4 Dinitrophenylhydrazone, *p*-nitrophenylhydrazone, semicarbazone and oxime derivatives of the base were prepared by the usual methods as described by Vogel⁶ and recrystallised from absolute alcohol. Yield of the derivatives was almost quantitative. Characteristics of the derivatives are noted in Table 2.

Isolation and analysis of Hg(II) chelate: On mixing equimolecular amounts of Hg(II) chloride and ligand (SB) in acetonitrile, dark blue complex was precipitated; solid was washed with minimum quantity of acetonitrile and ether successively and dried in vacuum desiccator over fused calcium chloride.

Chelate was analysed by usual methods and results of analysis are given in Table 3.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF SB

M.P. °C	Analysis		I.R. Stretching frequency		U.V. λ_{max}	
	Calc. (%)	Found (%)	> C = O (cm ⁻¹)	-CH = N (cm ⁻¹)	> C = O (nm)	> C = N (nm)
135	C = 78.14 H = 7.91 N = 6.53	77.46 7.39 6.41	1680	1603	240	216

TABLE 2—CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DERIVATIVES

2:4 Dinitrophenylhydrazone			<i>p</i> -Nitrophenylhydrazone			Semicarbazone			Oxime		
M.P. °C	Analysis		M.P. °C	Analysis		M.P. °C	Analysis		M.P. °C	Analysis	
	Calc. (%)	Found (%)		Calc. (%)	Found (%)		Calc. (%)	Found (%)		Calc. (%)	Found (%)
216	C = 60.76 H = 5.31 N = 17.72	60.59 5.18 17.63	180	C = 78.70 H = 7.54 N = 13.77	78.62 7.41 13.64	240	C = 66.18 H = 7.35 N = 20.59	65.98 7.28 20.44	204	C = 73.04 H = 7.82 N = 12.17	72.93 7.69 12.10

TABLE 3—CHARACTERISTICS OF COMPLEX

	Analysis		I.R. Stretching frequency		Magnetic moment (μ_B) B.M.	Molar conductance (Λ_M) Mhos.	Molecular weight
	Calc. (%)	Found (%)	> C = O (cm ⁻¹)	-CH = O (cm ⁻¹)			
	C = 34.52 H = 3.49 N = 2.87 Hg = 41.22	34.36 3.38 2.72 40.98	1625	1500	0.68	16.30	1108.85
Total	Cl = 14.59	14.40					
Ionic	Cl = 7.30	7.23					

Physico-Chemical measurements: Conductometric titration (Fig. 1) was performed by using Toshniwal conductivity bridge. 20 ml of $4.7 \times 10^{-3} M$ $HgCl_2$ solution in acetone was titrated against $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ ligand solution. Mercuric chloride solution was standardised gravimetrically with Thionalide⁶.

0.008M solution of chelate in nitrobenzene was used for molecular conductivity (Λ_M) determination. Magnetic measurements were taken on solution by using Quinke's method⁷ (Table 3). I.R. of SB (Table 1) and complex (Table 3) were recorded in KBr medium by using Perkin-Elmer Infra cord and U.V. was recorded in chloroform solution.

Discussions

In the I.R. spectra of base (SB) sharp bands at 1680 cm^{-1} and 1603 cm^{-1} are suggestive^{8,9} for the presence of $>C=O$ and $-CH=N$ groups in the compound. λ_{max} at $240\text{ m}\mu$ and $216\text{ m}\mu$ are higher than expected¹⁰ values for unconjugated $>C=O$ ($195\text{ m}\mu$) and for unconjugated $-CH=N$ ($190\text{ m}\mu$). Higher λ_{max} values are due to conjugation.

Inflexion point at 9.60 ml on the conductometric titration curve (Fig. 1) reveals that ligand (L) reacts with metal in ratio 1 : 1, which may also be verified by the analysis of the complex (Table 3).

the appearance of new metal-ligand bonds in the complex. On the basis of magnetic moment it is more likely to suggest tetrahedral stereochemistry to the complex under study. Tetrahedral stereochemistry of $Hg(II)$ complex is frequently reported¹¹⁻¹⁶ in several papers.

Molecular conductance value 16.3 Mhos in nitrobenzene (Table 3) corresponds to 1 : 1 electrolyte. Ethanolic solution of complex produces white precipitate of silver chloride on treatment with ethanolic silver nitrate solution. Gravimetric estimation of precipitated chloride ion verified 1 : 1 electrolytic nature of the complex.

Molecular weight of the complex was determined by the method 'freezing point depression' in nitrobenzene and value 1108.85 is suggestive that complex molecule is binuclear.

From the above results only following structure may be assigned to the complex.

Acknowledgement

We are indebted to Prof. J. P. Vajpai, D. S. College, Aligarh, for his worthy suggestions. Thanks are also

Fig. 1 Conductometric Titration

In the I.R. spectra of complex stretching frequencies of $>C=O$ and $-CH=N$ groups are 1625 cm^{-1} and 1500 cm^{-1} respectively which are lower than in pure SB. This lowering in stretching frequencies for $>C=O$ and $-CH=N$ groups in the complex may only be attributed to the metal-ligand interactions, with these groups as seats of interaction. These results suggest coordination through $C=O$ and $CH=N$ groups and formation of $Hg-O$ and $Hg-N$ bonds in the complex.

Magnetic moment (μ_e) value 0.68 BM is higher than spin-only value (0.00 BM) for diamagnetic $Hg(II)$ spin-paired system and may be attributed to

due to Mr. Rajendra Prasad and other friends for their sincere cooperation in carrying this work.

References

1. G. BAHR and A. KRETZER, *Z. anorg. allg. Chem.*, 1951, 267, 161.
2. G. BAHR and H. GEORG DOGE, *Z. anorg. allg. Chem.*, 1957, 292, 119.
3. G. BAHR and H. THAMLITZ, *Z. anorg. allg. Chem.*, 1955, 282, 3.
4. J. C. BAILLAR, JR. and E. J. FRIEHAUF, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1962, 24, 1405.

5. A. I. VOGEL, *A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry*, Longman Group Ltd., London, 1961.
6. A. I. VOGEL, *A Text Book of Inorganic Analysis* Longman Group Ltd., London, 1969.
7. A. EARNSHAW, *Introduction to Magneto Chemistry*, Academic Press, N.Y., 1968.
8. C. N. R. RAO, M. V. GEORGE, J. MAHANTY and P. T. NARASIMHAN, *A Hand Book of Chemistry and Physics*, Affiliated East-West Press, New Delhi.
9. C. N. R. RAO, *Chemical Applications of Infra Red Spectroscopy*, Academic Press, N.Y., 1963.
10. H. H. WILLARD, L. L. MERRITT, JR. and J. A. DEAN, *Instrumental Methods of Analysis*, D. Van Nostrand Co. Inc., N.Y., 1965.
11. L. E. ORGEL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 4186.
12. J. D. DUNITZ and L. E. ORGEL, *Adv. Inorg. Chem. and Radio Chem.*, 1960, 2, 1.
13. D. GRDENIC, *Quart. Rev.*, 1965, 19, 303.
14. R. S. NYHOLM, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 273.
15. L. E. ORGEL, *An Introduction to Transition Metal Chemistry Ligand-Field Theory* Methuen and Co. Ltd., London, 1963, p. 66.
16. S. N. PODDAR and K. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 47, 909.

of zinc from insulin in the form of chelates by these substances⁵. The antirheumatic action of salicylic acid has been attributed to the ability of this compound to complex with heavy metals and there is a positive relationship between the chelating ability and antithyroid activity among the thiouracils⁶. Tetramethylthiuram disulphide, the most active compound against pathogenic fungi, is also a good chelating agent⁷. Several chelating agents as well as their metal complexes have been examined for their antifungal activity⁸⁻¹⁰.

In view of the above findings, the present series of compounds were synthesised to find out the relation between the fungicidal activity and their ability for chelation with metals like copper, cobalt, nickel and zinc. The carboxymethyl and carboxyethyl thioureas were prepared by treatment of aryl isothiocyanates with glycine and β -alanine respectively. The infrared spectra of 1-carboxyethyl-3-*p*-tolyl-2-thiourea showed a sharp strong band at 3390 cm^{-1} (aryl-NH stretching), a broad band around 3200 cm^{-1} (NH stretching of the second NH group), a strong band at 1705 cm^{-1} (C=O stretching), characteristic bands of the benzene ring near 1600 and 1500 cm^{-1} and bands at 985 cm^{-1} , 1255 cm^{-1} and 1545 cm^{-1} due to C=S stretching¹¹. The other compounds in the series showed similar bands in close proximity to those listed above.

Studies on Potential Fungicides

Synthesis of Carboxymethyl and Carboxyethyl Thioureas

B. DASH & S. K. MAHAPATRA

Department of Chemistry, Utkal University, Bhubaneswar

Manuscript received 13 September 1972; revised 17 April 1973; accepted 30 August 1973

THE fungicidal action of sulphur containing compounds are well known. Several thiourea derivatives have been successfully screened for antibacterial¹, antifungal,^{2,3} antitubercular and anti-neoplastic⁴ activities. It has been observed that the biological activity of certain organic compounds is related to their ability for complex formation with metal ions. For example, the diabetogenic action of dithiazone, alloxan and oxine results from the removal

Experimental

1-Carboxyethyl-3[-p-chloro-phenyl]2-thioureas: A solution of 8.5 g. (0.05 mole) of *p*-chlorophenylisothiocyanate dissolved in minimum amount of alcohol and 4.45 g. (0.05 mole) of β -alanine in 100 ml. 1*N* NaOH in a 250 ml. conical flask was stirred at room temperature for 48 hr. The solution was filtered, cooled in icebath and acidified with 1 : 1 hydrochloric acid. The resulting white solid was washed with cold water and crystallised from alcohol, m.p.—154°. Yield 80% (Found : S, 12.02; N, 10.64; $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{SO}_2$ Cl requires S, 12.38; N, 10.83%).

The carboxymethylthioureas are prepared by the same procedure as given above by taking the corresponding isothiocyanates and glycine. The melting points, yields and analytical data of carboxymethylthioureas and other carboxyethylthioureas are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—1-CARBOXYALKYL-3-SUBSTITUTED-2-THIOUREAS $\text{RNHCSNH}(\text{CH}_2)_n\text{COOH}$

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	n = 1		% Nitrogen Found	% Nitrogen Calc.	M.P. °C	Yield %	n = 2		% Nitrogen Found	% Nitrogen Calc.
				% Sulphur Found	% Sulphur Calc.					% Sulphur Found	% Sulphur Calc.		
1.	C_6H_5	141	80	14.74	15.23	12.82	13.34						
2.	<i>p</i> - $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	157	85	13.84	14.29	12.02	12.50	130	80	13.23	13.45	11.51	11.77
3.	<i>o</i> - $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	155	85	13.78	14.29	12.13	12.50	153	85	13.14	13.45	11.47	11.77
4.	<i>m</i> - $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	170	80	13.73	14.29	12.04	12.50	138	80	13.16	13.45	11.42	11.77
5.	<i>p</i> - $\text{OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	146	85	12.97	13.33	11.25	11.67						
6.	<i>o</i> - $\text{OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$							145	75	12.32	12.60	10.72	11.03
7.	<i>m</i> - $\text{OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	160	80	12.91	13.33	11.16	11.67	125	75	12.14	12.60	10.61	11.03
8.	<i>p</i> - BrC_6H_4							156	75	10.15	10.56	8.73	9.24
9.	<i>p</i> - ClC_6H_4	180	75	12.71	13.08	11.02	11.45						
10.	<i>p</i> - $\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	127	75	12.14	12.60	10.51	11.03						
11.	α -naphthyl	150	70	11.85	12.30	10.22	10.76						
12.	β -naphthyl	162	70	11.92	12.30	10.13	10.76						